

THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX TOWPREG PRODUCTION

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SUMMARY

This work establishes the process windows for efficient towpreg production on a recently developed powder coating equipment. Three different thermoplastic towpregs were studied: one for highly demanding markets (carbon fibre/Primospire) and other two for commercial applications (glass/polypropylene and glass/polyvinyl chloride). Mechanical properties of compression moulded composites obtained from the produced towpregs were also obtained and discussed.

Keywords: Towpreg, Thermoplastic, Composite, Primospire, powder coating

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites have been successfully employed in the aircraft, military and aerospace industries due to the excellent properties [1]. In these and many other commercial engineering applications, they can replace other materials, such as thermosetting matrix composites. However, the high cost of the impregnation of continuous fibre thermoplastic composites, arising from the melting of the polymer or the use of solvents, still restricts their use in commercial applications. Hence, cost reduction largely depends on developing more efficient methods for impregnating fibres with high-viscosity thermoplastics and for processing final composite parts.

In this work, a dry coating process developed previously [2-5] was modified to produce at low cost pre-impregnated glass or carbon fibres powdered with thermoplastic matrices (towpregs) at industrial scale processing rates.

Composites were processed from produced towpregs by compression moulding using glass and carbon fibres reinforced polypropylene and polyvinyl chloride for common engineering applications and carbon fibre reinforced Primospire, which is an amorphous highly aromatic thermoplastic polymer developed by Solvay Advanced Polymers, for application in highly advanced markets [5-8]. Good examples of advanced market applications are the manufacture of composite overwrapped pressure vessels used in space such as pressurised tanks for rocket trust vector control systems, propellant pressurisation, cold gas propulsion and liquid propellant storage systems and structural components for the new generation of Reusable Launching Vehicles (RLV).

EXPERIMENTAL

Powder coating line

The designed prototype powder coating equipment used in this work to produce glass and carbon fibre reinforced towpregs is schematically depicted in Figure 1. It consists of six main parts: a wind-off system, a fibres spreader unit, a heating section, a coating section, a consolidation unit and a wind-up section. In order to produce the desired amounts of pre-impregnated material, the process starts by winding-off fibres from their tows. In the next stage, the fibres pass through a pneumatic spreader and are heated in a convection oven. Immediately after, the heated fibres pass into a vibrating bath of polymer powder and therefore being coated. A gravity system allows maintaining constant the amount of polymer powder. The oven of the consolidation unit allows softening the polymer powder, promoting its adhesion to the fibre surface. Finally, the thermoplastic matrix towpreg is cooled down and wound-up on the final spool.

Figure 1 - Schematic diagram of the powder-coating line set-up

The photograph depicted in Figure 2 shows a general overview of the developed powder coating equipment.

Figure 2 – Photo of the developed powder coating equipment

Materials

2400 Tex type E glass fibre rovings, from Owens Corning, 1600 Tex carbon fibre tows, from Tenax (HTA 5131) and polypropylene, from ICO Polymers France (Icorene 9184B P), and polyvinyl chloride, supplied by CIRES (PVC - PREVINIL AG 736), powders were used to produce GF/PP, CF/PP and GF/PVC towpregs to be applied in common composite engineering parts. Table 1 summarises the most relevant properties of these materials.

Table 1 - Properties of materials used in towpregs for common applications

Property	Units	Glass fibres	Carbon fibres	Polypropylene	PVC
Density	Mg/m ³	2.56	1.77	0.91	1.4
Tensile strength	MPa	3500	3785	30	55
Tensile modulus	GPa	76	234	1.3	3.0
Average powder particle size	µm	-	-	440	150
Linear roving weight	Tex	2400	1600	-	-

To produce towpregs for highly demanding advanced markets a new polymer developed by Solvay Advanced Polymers (PRIMOSPIRE[®] PR 120) and carbon fibre tows from TORAYCA (760 Tex M30SC) were used in this work. The densities of fibres and polymer were 1.73 Mg/m³ and 1.21 Mg/m³, respectively. Table 2 presents the most relevant properties determined on these raw materials.

Table 2 - Properties of materials used in towpregs for more advanced applications

Property	Units	Carbon fibres	Primospire
Density	Mg/m ³	1.73	1.21
Tensile strength	MPa	2833	104.3
Tensile modulus	GPa	200	8.0
Average powder particle size	µm	-	139.4
Linear roving weight	Tex	760	-

Processing conditions

Table 3 summarises the experimental results determined to study the influence of the powder coating line speed on the polymer mass fraction obtained in the continuous carbon (CF/PP) and glass fibres (GF/PP) reinforced polypropylene towpregs produced for application in common commercial markets, respectively. To determine polymer fraction obtained in the final towpregs, 1 m length towpreg strips were cut and weighted during the coating line operation.

Table 3 - Production speed versus towpreg polymer contents

Linear fibre pull speed (m/min)	Polymer mass fraction (%)	
	GF/PP towpreg	CF/PP towpreg
2.0	32.4±8.5	20.0±0.1
4.0	30.4±4.3	15.8±0.8
6.0	29.5±5.2	24.8±0.1

From results shown in Table 3 it may be conclude that a reduction in polymer deposition with pull-speed was observed, as expected, in the case glass fibres but such behaviour was not found for the CF/PP towpregs. This latter unexpected behaviour is probably related to the higher temperature that carbon fibres exhibit during the powder polymer bath impregnation due the shorter cooling stage time they experienced between the exit of convection oven and the powder polymer basin at higher pull-speed. Even if more studies should be carried out to in order to better understand this phenomenon, it is promising to observe that production rate speeds between 2.0 and 6.0 m/min may be used to produce GF/PP and CF/PP towpregs with polymer mass contents compatible with the major common commercial engineering applications.

Figure 3 also show the same type of results for the glass fibre reinforced polyvinyl chloride (GF/PVC) produced towpregs. As may be seen in this Figure high levels of PVC polymer content were also obtained for production rate speeds between 2.0 and 6.0 m/min which makes the developed coating process attractive for the commercial engineering application of the GF/PVC towpregs.

Figure 3 - Production speed versus polymer content in GF/PVC towpregs

The variation of the polymer mass fraction in the carbon fibre reinforced Primospire (CF/Primospire) towpregs with fibre pull speed may be seen in Figure 4. As expected, the amounts of polymer powder decreases with the increase of the production

speed. Enough amount of Primospire was obtained for production speeds until 4 m/min in the case of these advanced market towpregs.

Figure 4 - Variation of the polymer mass fraction in the CF/Primospire towpreg with fibre pull speed

Typical temperatures of 315° C, 400°C and 620°C were used in the coating line initial convection oven in the above experiments made with towpregs using the PP, PVC and Primospire as thermoplastic matrices, respectively.

Consolidation by compression moulding

A technique described elsewhere [9] was used to produce unidirectional fibre reinforced laminate plates with 100×100×4 mm directly from the towpregs. First, the towpreg were wound over a plate with appropriate dimensions and the resultant pre-form then conveniently placed in the cavity of a heated mould. A 400 kN SATIM hot platen press was used to obtain the desired consolidation pressure. After heating the cavity, pressure was applied and, finally, the mould was cooled down to room temperature and the final composite laminate plate removed.

Composites flexural properties

Accordingly to ISO 178 standard, three-point bending tests in fibre direction were made on five 100 × 15 × 4 (mm) specimens obtained from the composites plates processed by compression moulding using an universal INSTRON 4505 testing machine. The tests were performed at 2 mm/min cross head speed using a distance between supports of 80 mm. The fibre mass fraction was also determined according to EN 60.

Table 4 summarizes the experimental results obtained for the different materials used in this work.

Table 4 - Properties of composites from towpregs

Property	Units	GF/PP	CF/PP	GF/PVC	CF/Primospire
Flexural strength	MPa	66.3±9.4	104.5±5.2	62.2±6.9	124.3±15.0
Flexural modulus	GPa	24.7±2.6	27.7±3.6	17.6±0.9	30.0±5.0
Fibre mass fraction	%	85.6±1.6	55.4±1.2	57.7±1.1	59.7±0.3

As may be seen, flexural properties compatible with the applications envisaged for the composites processed from the produced towpregs were obtained in this preliminary work. In future, better properties may be certainly obtained through the improvement of fibre/matrix adhesion, polymer powder distribution and fibre alignment.

CONCLUSIONS

A new prototype powder-coating equipment suitable to produce in good conditions towpregs for common and advanced engineering markets has been successfully developed and tested in this work. From the initial tests made, it was found that those towpregs can be easily and continuously produced at speeds between 2 a 6 m/min that are adequate for industrial production scale.

For common engineering markets glass fibre reinforced polypropylene and polyvinyl chloride matrix as well as carbon fibre reinforced polypropylene towpregs were studied. Carbon fibre reinforced Primospire towpregs were also considered envisaging advanced composite structural markets.

Already enough good mechanical properties were obtained from the preliminary tests made on the unidirectional and woven fabric fibre reinforced composites easily processed by compression moulding from the produced towpregs. However, further work is currently been carried to improve these properties and optimise the composite processing cycles.

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